

Relationship between leaf dry weight and root dry weight. 1 = 15 days after sowing (DS), 2 = 30 DS, 3 = 45 DS, 4 = 60 DS, 5 = 75 DS, 6 = 90 DS, 7 = 105 DS.

most balanced in Jhona 349, a reportedly salt-resistant variety. The low-yielding Basmati 320 and Basmati 198 deviated most by producing either low leaf-to-root weights for the former or low root-to-leaf weights for the latter (see figure). IR8, Basmati 6129, and IR6 also showed

moderately good relationships in terms of root-to-leaf weight production. Varietal screening for balanced growth of root-to-leaf weight may be helpful in identifying gene pools suitable for growth in diverse situations. ■

Diallel analysis of plant height, tiller number, and panicle length in rice

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Genetic information obtained by diallel analysis of some rices revealed additive type of gene action for plant height and tiller number and complete dominance type of gene action for panicle length in a study conducted with some traditional and modern rices and their F_1 progenies. Jhona 349, a traditional type, possessed most of the dominant alleles for plant

height and tiller number, whereas IR6 possessed an excess of the dominant alleles for panicle length. IR6, IR8, and Basmati 320 had most of the recessive alleles for plant height and tiller number, while Jhona 349 had an excess of the recessive alleles for panicle length. Basmati 320 and IR8 had also many dominant alleles for panicle length.

Diallel analysis of the same rices and their F_1 progenies revealed overdominance type of gene action for number of spikelets per panicle, number of grains per panicle, and additive type of gene action for panicle weight. IR6 and IR8 had most of the dominant alleles for number of spikelets per panicle and number of grains per panicle, while Jhona 349 had an excess of dominant alleles for grain weight. Basmati 320 had an excess of the recessive alleles for number of spikelets per panicle and number of grains per panicle. Basmati 320, IR6, and IR8 had most of the recessive alleles for grain weight.

Rice cultivars possessing some desirable floral traits influencing outcrossing

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Although F_1 hybrid rice varieties have been successfully developed and cultivated in China, the ease and cost of the production of hybrid seed would determine to what extent the approach can be employed to develop high yielding hybrids in other rice-growing countries of the world. The floral structure of rice is not well-adapted to cross-pollination and less than 1% natural outcrossing is observed normally. On male-sterile plants, however, up to 33–45% seed set has been obtained in China. Several floral traits – stigma size, stigma exertion, duration of opening of spikelet, and anther size and filament length – are known to influence outcrossing in rice. In the hybrid rice research program at IRRI, 86 elite breeding lines were studied for stigma length, stigma breadth, stigma exertion, anther length, anther breadth, and filament length. There was sufficient

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Variability in floral traits influencing outcrossing among 86 selected rice varieties and breeding lines. IRRI, 1980.

variability among rice varieties with regard to the floral characteristics studied (see figure). Eleven rice cultivars possessing some desirable floral traits influencing outcrossing were identified: BG90-2, BPI 121-407, CR179-1-717,

IR46, IR2307-247-2-2-3, IR8236-B-B-572-1, IR13188-9, IR13423-10-2-3, IR17492-18-1-2-2, IR17494-32-2-2-1-3, and IR17494-32-3-1-1-3. These cultivars are being used in the IRRI hybrid breeding program. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Bacterial foot rot of rice

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Bacterial foot rot disease was first found infecting a few plants of IR36 in IRRI fields in 1977; its incidence has not

increased since. A similar disease was reported in Korea and in India in 1979. Although the disease may have spread fairly widely, difficulty of recognition and identification of the causal bacterium may have handicapped realization of its presence.

Previous reports indicated that the causal pathogen was bacterial. IRRI

studies indicate that the disease IS caused by bacteria quite similar to *Erwinia chrysanthemi*, which causes bacterial cornstalk rot. Isolates from both rice and maize incited typical stalk rot on both crops by cross inoculation. Their general bacteriological characteristics are also similar to those of *E. chrysanthemi*. Four colony variants, distinguished on peptone sucrose agar medium, all incited the disease on rice as well as on maize. A distinct blue pigment was produced on slices of maize stalks by the maize isolates — but not by the rice isolates — at 20°C but not at higher temperatures. The blue pigmentation may be a specific characteristic of the maize isolates different from that of the rice isolates. However, other tests, including colony morphology on crystal violet pectate medium, growth at 36°C, α-methyl glucoside and phosphatase reactions all indicated that the rice isolates from the Philippines were similar to those from Japan and Korea, and those of *E. chrysanthemi* cause cornstalk rot. Bacterial foot rot of rice is therefore similar to the foot rot of rice found in Japan. ■

Coefficient of correlation between two scoring systems and the reaction of resistant varieties in Japan to pathotypes of *Xanthomonas oryzae* in the Philippines

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The coefficients of correlation between Ezuka and Horino's scale for bacterial blight resistance and that of the IRRI Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES) for bacterial blight were compared on infection incited by the clipping and pin-pricking inoculations. The results were highly significant.

Using the two scoring systems, 48 varieties from Japan and the Philippines classified into different varietal groups according to resistance to virulence of the bacteria were tested in the greenhouse and in the field against 4 Philippine pathotypes of *X. oryzae*. The varieties